

Seminar Paper

Optimizing Power Plant Expansion under Uncertainty: A Stochastic Programming Approach

Akshay Singh Yadav

Born on: 6th October 1993 in India
Matriculation number: 5192890

Christian Tsenov

Born on: 14th January 1999 in Bulgaria
Matriculation number: 5195954

Rishabh Tiwari

Born on: 13th September 1999 in India
Matriculation number: 5197818

Sebastian Trümper

Born on: 13th September 1990 in Germany
Matriculation number: 3631139

15th September 2024

Supervisors

Dr. Hannes Hobbie

Mr. Andreas Büttner

Supervising professor

Prof. Dr. Dominik Möst

Abstract

This study presents a stochastic optimization model for power plant expansion planning in Germany, considering uncertainties in future electricity demand driven by electric vehicle (EV) charging patterns. The model aims to minimize total system costs while meeting environmental constraints and ensuring supply reliability in the context of Germany's ongoing energy transition. We employ a two-stage stochastic programming approach, incorporating three demand scenarios based on different EV charging strategies: home charging, combined home and work charging, and smart charging. The model optimizes investment decisions for various power generation technologies, including renewables, conventional plants, and storage systems. Our results demonstrate the differences between stochastic and deterministic approaches in addressing demand uncertainties. The stochastic model proposes a different energy mix compared to the deterministic model, particularly in the capacity of gas-fired plants. The study also examines the potential impacts of different EV charging strategies on the future energy mix.

Key findings include:

- 1. The stochastic solution differs from the deterministic approach in terms of proposed build capacities, especially for gas-fired plants.
- 2. The model calculates the Value of Stochastic Solution (VSS) and Expected Value of Perfect Information (EVPI), providing insights into the value of considering uncertainty in planning.
- 3. Different EV charging scenarios lead to variations in proposed build capacities, particularly for solar and wind technologies.

This research contributes to energy planning in Germany by modeling the impact of demand uncertainties on investment decisions. The findings have implications for policymakers and energy planners in designing strategies to support Germany's energy transition goals while considering system reliability and cost-effectiveness.

Table of Contents

Abstract	I
List of Figures	IV
List of Tables	V
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background on Germany's Energy Sector and Challenges	1
1.2 Motivating EV-Driven Demand Uncertainty as a Key Factor in Power System Planning	1
1.3 Research objective	2
2 Literature Review	4
2.1 Demand Uncertainty and EV Charging Strategies	4
2.2 Stochastic Programming in Energy Systems	4
2.3 Load Forecasting and Demand-Side Management	5
2.4 Renewable Energy Integration	5
2.5 Remarks	6
3 Model and Methods	7
3.1 Methodology	7
3.1.1 Objective Function	7
3.1.2 Constraints	7
3.1.3 Stochastic Nature of the Problem	9
3.2 Data and Model Inputs	10
3.2.1 Description of Key Parameters	10
3.2.2 Scenario Distribution	10
4 Results and Analysis	12
4.1 Objective and Problem Formulation	12
4.1.1 Expected Value Solution	12
4.1.2 Perfect Information Solution	13
4.1.3 Stochastic Solution	14
4.2 Cost Component Analysis	14
4.2.1 Investment Costs	14
4.2.2 Generation Costs	15
4.2.3 Load Shedding Costs	15

4.3	Model Parameters	15
4.3.1	Value of Stochastic Solution (VSS)	15
4.3.2	Expected Value of Perfect Information (EVPI)	15
4.4	Comparing Build Capacities	16
4.5	Comparing Power Generation	17
4.6	Build Capacities in Perfect Information Case	18
5	Conclusion	20
6	Appendix	22
	Bibliography	24

List of Figures

4.1	Break-up of the cost components under various assumptions of solution techniques	14
4.2	Total cost under various assumptions of solution techniques, values of VSS and EVPI	16
4.3	Comparison of build capacities between stochastic and deterministic solutions . . .	16
4.4	Power generated by individual technologies: Comparison between stochastic and deterministic solutions	18
4.5	Build Capacities under the Perfect Information Assumption	19

List of Tables

4.1	Build Capacities and Percentage Share of Different Technologies Considering Expected Value of Demand	13
A.1	Power Plant Investment Data	22
A.2	Power Plant Operational Costs and Emission Factors	22
A.3	Data sources for the analysis	23

List of Symbols

Sets & Indices

Sets

t	Time periods, $t \in \{t_1, \dots, t_{8761}\}$
s	demand scenario, $s \in \{s_1, s_2, s_3\}$
p	Plant types, $p \in \{windOff, windOn, water, \dots, oil\}$
p_c	Conventional plants, $cp \subseteq p$
p_b	Base load plants, $bp \subseteq p$
p_r	Renewable plants, $rp \subseteq p$
p_{cip}	Constrained investment plants, $cip \subseteq p$
p_s	Storage plants, $st \subseteq p$
p_{s1}	Alias for stage one scenarios
p_{s2}	Alias for stage two scenarios

Parameters

$d(t)$	Power demand at time t
$w_s(s)$	probability of scenario s
$scap_{st}$	Storage capacity for storage st
$cap(p)$	Installed capacities for plant p
$cf(p, t)$	Capacity factor for plant p at time t
$capf(p_r, t)$	Capacity factor for renewable plant p at time t
$capw(p_w)$	Capacity factor for water based plants
$af(p, t)$	Availability of plant p , at time t
$ef(p)$	Carbon emissions for plant p
$cef(p)$	Carbon emission efficiency factor for plant p
cep	Carbon emission price p
$ic(p)$	Annual investment costs for plant p
$oc(p)$	Operational costs for plant p
$voll$	Value of lost load per MWh

Variables

TC	Total cost
$PO(t, st)$	Pump operation in storage plants during time t
$C_{CO_2}(p)$	Carbon emissions from plant p
$C_{cost}(p)$	Carbon emission costs for plant p
$PG(s, t, p)$	Power generation in scenario s , time t , plant p
$SL(s, t, st)$	Storage loading in scenario s , time t , storage st
$SG(s, t, st)$	Storage generation in scenario s , time t , storage st
$LS(s, t)$	load shedding in scenario s , time t
$BL(p)$	Total base load for plant p
IC_{add}	Additional investment costs
$EVPI$	Expected value of perfect information
VSS	Value of stochastic solution
Z_{PI}	Objective value for perfect information
Z_{DP}	Objective value for deterministic programming or expected value solution
Z_{SS}	Objective value for stochastic programming

1 Introduction

1.1 Background on Germany's Energy Sector and Challenges

Germany's energy sector is undergoing a significant transformation, driven by the ambitious "Energiewende" policy, which targets a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and an increase in renewable energy capacity. As of 2023, Germany has completely phased out nuclear power, marking a historic milestone in its energy transition. This leaves the country heavily reliant on renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar, which now account for a substantial portion of its energy mix. In 2023, renewables made up more than 50% of Germany's electricity production, with wind energy contributing the largest share (*Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz (BMWK), 2024*). However, this shift comes with considerable challenges, particularly in ensuring grid stability and supply security while phasing out coal by 2038 and aiming for carbon neutrality by 2045 (*Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz (BMWK), 2024*).

The phase-out of nuclear energy and the planned coal exit have intensified the need for investment in new infrastructure, especially in energy storage and transmission systems. The geographical mismatch between renewable energy production, largely concentrated in northern Germany, and consumption hubs in the south further complicates this transition. As renewable sources are variable by nature, balancing supply and demand requires flexible solutions, including gas-fired plants, energy storage, and advanced grid management technologies.

Simultaneously, the energy transition must balance environmental goals with economic considerations, managing the costs associated with new infrastructure development and ensuring the competitiveness of the German industry. Public acceptance of new energy infrastructure, such as transmission lines and wind farms, also remains a significant hurdle.

1.2 Motivating EV-Driven Demand Uncertainty as a Key Factor in Power System Planning

The transformation of Germany's energy sector is occurring in an environment characterized by multiple uncertainties. These uncertainties span various domains, including demand fluctuations, renewable energy output variability, fuel and carbon price volatility, technological developments, and potential policy changes at both domestic and EU levels.

A particularly pressing source of uncertainty in the current energy landscape is the rapid increase in electric vehicle (EV) adoption, which introduces significant variability in electricity demand. EV charging strategies play a crucial role in shaping the demand profile, as different charging patterns can lead to widely varying load curves. For instance, home-based charging often results in higher demand during evening hours, when electricity consumption is already at its peak. In contrast, workplace charging or smart charging strategies, which align EV charging with periods of high renewable energy availability, can help flatten the demand curve and reduce pressure on the grid (Boßmann and Staffell, 2015). This uncertainty around when and where EV charging will occur adds a new dimension to power system planning, making it essential to incorporate flexible and resilient solutions. By focusing on demand uncertainty driven by EV adoption, this research captures the critical impact of different charging behaviors on grid dynamics, ensuring that future power systems are robust enough to handle these emerging challenges.

1.3 Research objective

The primary objective of this research is to develop a robust and adaptable model for power plant operations and expansion planning in Germany. The model specifically addresses the uncertainties introduced by the increasing adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) and the variability of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar. These uncertainties play a significant role in shaping both the demand profile and the supply-side capabilities of the energy system, necessitating a flexible approach to ensure efficient and reliable energy planning.

By using stochastic programming, this research aims to optimize power plant investments and operational strategies across multiple potential future scenarios. These scenarios, driven by different EV charging patterns—such as home charging, workplace charging, and smart charging—introduce significant variability into electricity demand. The stochastic approach enables the model to account for this variability, ensuring that power plant operations are optimized to meet demand fluctuations while minimizing costs and maintaining grid stability.

The key research question guiding this study is:

How can stochastic programming optimize power plant operations and expansion planning by accounting for uncertainties in EV-driven demand and fluctuating renewable energy output?

Addressing this question allows the study to explore the advantages of stochastic programming

over deterministic methods. By considering multiple future scenarios, the model provides insights into the impact of demand uncertainty on system costs, power generation, and the future energy mix. The findings of this research offer valuable guidance for policymakers and energy planners as they navigate the complexities of Germany's ongoing energy transition.

2 Literature Review

The transition toward a low-carbon energy system in Germany is shaped by increasing renewable energy adoption and the electrification of sectors such as transport, which introduces significant uncertainties in electricity demand and supply. This chapter reviews the key literature that supports the stochastic modeling approach used in this research, focusing on demand-side uncertainties, EV charging strategies, renewable energy integration, and stochastic methods in energy systems.

2.1 Demand Uncertainty and EV Charging Strategies

Boßmann and Staffell, 2015 present a detailed analysis of future electricity demand in Germany and Britain, specifically focusing on how the increasing penetration of electric vehicles (EVs) and heat pumps will reshape the demand curve. Their study uses models such as eLOAD and DESSTinEE to simulate future hourly load curves, showing that EV adoption significantly influences peak demand patterns. *Koreneff et al., 2009* further analyze the impact of different EV charging behaviors in the Nordic countries, showing that smart charging strategies can reduce the load on the grid by aligning charging times with periods of high renewable energy generation.

Andersen et al., 2013 discuss the importance of understanding the systematic variations in hourly electricity demand profiles and highlight the role of different customer categories in shaping the aggregated load profile. Using data from Denmark, they demonstrate that as consumption technologies like electric vehicles and heat pumps are adopted, the long-term aggregated load profile will change significantly. The authors argue that future energy system models must consider these changes, as the introduction of new consumption technologies alters the hourly load profile as well as total annual consumption, making long-term load forecasting crucial for energy system planning.

2.2 Stochastic Programming in Energy Systems

Stochastic programming offers a robust way to handle the uncertainties introduced by renewable energy variability and fluctuating demand patterns. *Möst and Keles, 2010* provide a comprehensive review of stochastic modeling approaches in liberalized electricity markets. They outline the various risks and uncertainties faced by power generation companies due to market liberalization

and increased renewable energy integration, such as electricity price volatility and fuel price fluctuations. The authors emphasize the need for stochastic models to support decision-making under uncertainty, especially in long-term system optimization.

Conejo et al., 2010 delve into the practical applications of stochastic programming for electricity markets. Their work provides tools and models for market participants to make informed decisions under uncertainty. These models enable electricity producers to develop offering strategies for the pool market, while retailers and consumers can use stochastic methods to optimize their energy procurement strategies across different trading floors. The stochastic models presented in this work are highly applicable for managing the inherent uncertainties in both electricity generation and market participation.

2.3 Load Forecasting and Demand-Side Management

Long-term load forecasting is critical for energy system planning, as it accounts for future uncertainties in both demand and supply. *Andersen et al., 2013* contribute to this field by presenting econometric models that forecast future electricity demand based on macroeconomic variables, customer categories, and new consumption technologies. Their study emphasizes the importance of linking demand profiles with broader energy system models, especially when considering the rise of EVs and heat pumps. This integration is essential for ensuring that long-term system planning accurately reflects future demand patterns.

2.4 Renewable Energy Integration

As Germany pushes toward an 80% share of renewable energy in gross electricity consumption by 2030, integrating variable renewable energy sources (vRES) such as wind and solar becomes a central challenge. The recent report by the Bundesministerium für *Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz (BMWK), 2024* highlights the progress made in achieving more than 50% renewable energy generation as of 2023 and outlines the government's strategy to accelerate the energy transition. This increasing reliance on renewables introduces significant uncertainties into the grid, particularly due to the intermittent nature of wind and solar power.

Möst and Keles, 2010 briefly address the challenges of integrating fluctuating renewable energy into power systems, emphasizing the need for stochastic methods that can capture the variability of renewable generation. The focus on scenario generation and reduction is particularly relev-

ant for handling large datasets of renewable output, ensuring that system planning models can accommodate the variability in supply.

2.5 Remarks

The literature reviewed in this chapter demonstrates the importance of incorporating demand-side and supply-side uncertainties in power system planning. Stochastic programming, in particular, offers a flexible and resilient framework for optimizing power plant operations and expansion under uncertain conditions. The studies discussed here, along with recent government reports, form the basis for the modeling approach and scenario development used in this research.

3 Model and Methods

3.1 Methodology

This section provides a detailed description of the optimization model used to simulate the power system's operations, focusing on minimizing the total system cost while adhering to technical and environmental constraints. The model incorporates stochastic scenarios to account for uncertainties, in form of varying demand across different time periods.

3.1.1 Objective Function

The objective is to minimize the total cost (TC), which includes both the operational and emission costs of power plants and storage facilities as well as the investment costs for new capacities:

$$\begin{aligned} \min TC = & \sum_{s,t,p} (w_s \cdot PG(s,t,p) \cdot oc(p)) + \sum_p (ic(p) \cdot BC(p)) \\ & + \sum_{t,s} (w_s \cdot LS(s,t) \cdot voll) + \sum_{s,t,p} (w_s \cdot PG(s,t,p) \cdot ef(p) \cdot cef(p) \cdot cop) \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

3.1.2 Constraints

Energy Balance Constraint

The energy balance ensures that the total power generation meet the demand for each time period and scenario:

$$\sum_p PG(s,t,p) + LS(s,t) = \sum_s d(s,t) + \sum_{p_s} SL(s,t,p_s) \quad (3.2)$$

Generation Capacity Constraints

The power generation from plant p is constrained by its available capacity, which includes both existing and newly built capacities, as well as the plant's availability factor:

$$PG(s,t,p) \leq (cap(p) + BC(p)) \cdot af(p,t) \quad (3.3)$$

$$LS(s, t, p) \leq PG(s, t, p) \quad (3.4)$$

The generation capacity constraint (3.3) ensures that power generation does not exceed the sum of the existing capacity $cap(p)$ and newly built capacity $BC(p)$, adjusted by the availability factor $af(p)$. Additionally, load shedding at any stage would be lesser than the generated output (Equation 3.4).

Renewable Power Generation Constraints

Renewable power plants generation, in particular solar and wind based plants, are dependant on the environment. To achieve a more realistic generation curve a capacity factor is applied.

$$PG(s, t, p_r) \leq (cap(p_r) + BC(p_r)) \cdot capf(p_r) \quad (3.5)$$

Storage Constraints

For storage facilities, the energy balance must also hold. The level of stored energy at any time period depends on the storage level in the previous period, the amount of energy charged, and the energy generated by the storage unit:

$$SL(s, t, st) = SL(s, t - 1, st) + SL(s, t - 1, st) - PG(s, t, st) \quad (3.6)$$

The storage level is bounded by the maximum storage capacity:

$$SL(s, t, st) \leq scap_{st} + BC(st) \quad (3.7)$$

Constraints (3.6) and (3.7) model the storage dynamics, ensuring that the storage levels are updated based on the energy charged and discharged. The charge and discharge rate is limited by the following equation

$$SL(s, t, st) \leq (scap_{st} + BC(st)) \div 6 \quad (3.8)$$

$$PG(s, t, st) \leq (scap_{st} + BC(st)) \div 6 \quad (3.9)$$

Ramping Constraints for Baseload Plants

To ensure realistic baseload plants, a limit is implemented how much the power output can increase or decrease between consecutive time periods:

$$PG(s, t, p_b) \leq PG(s, t - 1, p_b) + 0.18 \cdot (cap(p_b) + BC(p_b)) \quad (3.10)$$

$$PG(s, t, p_b) \geq PG(s, t - 1, p_b) - 0.18 \cdot (cap(p_b) + BC(p_b)) \quad (3.11)$$

The ramping constraints (3.10) and (3.11) ensure that the baseload plants do not change their output drastically within short periods.

Water constraints

Water based power generation facilities can not be build everywhere. There are preconditions that have to be fulfilled. The upper limit is then calculated as follows:

$$\sum_{p_{cip}} cap(p_{cip}) \cdot capw(p_w) \geq \sum_{p_{cip}} cap(p_{cip}) + BC(p_{cip}) \quad (3.12)$$

3.1.3 Stochastic Nature of the Problem

The model incorporates uncertainty through the use of multiple scenarios s , each representing different possible future states (e.g., varying demand levels). Each scenario has an associated probability w_s , which reflects the likelihood of that scenario occurring. The objective function (3.1) and constraints (3.2 to 3.12) are evaluated across all scenarios, with the total cost being weighted by the scenario probabilities.

This stochastic approach allows the model to account for uncertainties in demand profile, ensuring a more robust solution that minimizes costs across various possible futures rather than optimizing

for a single deterministic outcome.

3.2 Data and Model Inputs

3.2.1 Description of Key Parameters

The model uses hourly time periods over the course of a year (t_1 to t_{8760}). It considers three demand scenarios (s_1 , s_2 , s_3) with probabilities of 0.5, 0.3, and 0.2, respectively.

The different types of power plants in the model include conventional plants (e.g., lignite, nuclear, gas), renewable energy plants (e.g., wind, solar, water, biomass), and storage technologies (e.g., pumped storage, battery). Investment in nuclear power, biomass, storage, water and reservoir storages are constrained. Conventional power plants are further categorized into base load plants, which provide continuous power generation. The probability distribution across scenarios reflects the uncertainty in future demand profiles. Please refer to Appendix A and B for the values of parametric data input to the model.

3.2.2 Scenario Distribution

The demand profile for the three scenarios is adapted from the work of Boßmann and Staffell (*Boßmann and Staffell, 2015*), which explores future electricity demand patterns in Germany and Britain in the 2050s. Thus, the model incorporates three distinct demand scenarios, each representing varying patterns of electric vehicle (EV) charging, which influence the energy demand profile and grid dynamics.

- **Scenario 1 (Home Charging):** This scenario assumes that EVs are predominantly charged at home, during the evening when residential electricity consumption is at its peak. It has the highest probability of 0.5, reflecting its central importance in the model. The concentrated demand from home charging increases the load during hours when renewable energy is less available, leading to higher reliance on flexible and backup power sources.
- **Scenario 2 (Home and Work Charging):** In this scenario, EV charging is distributed between home and workplaces. This results in a more balanced demand profile, with reduced peaks in the evening as some of the demand is shifted to earlier hours when workplace charging occurs. The probability assigned to this scenario is 0.3, recognizing the potential for future expansion of workplace charging infrastructure.
- **Scenario 3 (Smart Charging):** This scenario envisions the implementation of smart charging

strategies that optimize EV charging times to better align with periods of high renewable energy availability, such as during peak solar or wind generation. Smart charging reduces the need for non-renewable backup power and smooths out demand fluctuations. It is the least likely scenario, with a probability of 0.2, due to its reliance on advanced technologies and regulatory support.

4 Results and Analysis

4.1 Objective and Problem Formulation

The primary goal of the model is to minimize the total cost, which includes the investment cost for constructing new power plants, the variable costs associated with electricity generation and transmission, and the cost of load shedding due to unserved demand, also known as the value of lost load. The problem can be formulated in various ways, depending on the availability and reliability of data. A common approach, particularly when reliable future demand data is lacking, is to use the expected demand and solve the problem as a capacity expansion model. This represents the simplest scenario, where there is no knowledge of future market behavior or uncertainty. The resulting cost is referred to as the expected value solution or deterministic problem and is denoted by Z_{DP} .

In the ideal case where perfect information about future scenarios is available, the model can determine optimal capacity expansion decisions based on the exact demand in a future stage. The cost under this scenario would naturally be lower than Z_{DP} , and this cost is denoted as Z_{PI} .

The stochastic model offers a compromise between these two extremes. In this case, limited information about the future is incorporated in the form of probability distributions for known demand outcomes. The cost for this stochastic solution lies between Z_{DP} and Z_{PI} , providing a more realistic estimate under uncertainty. In the following sections, we elaborate on the three approaches to the problem.

4.1.1 Expected Value Solution

The expected value solution is obtained by replacing the demand in Equation (3.2) with its expected value, resulting in the modified form shown in Equation (4.1):

$$\sum_p PG(t, p) + LS(t) = \sum_s w_s(s) \cdot d(t) + \sum_{p_s} SL(t, p_s) \quad (4.1)$$

In this formulation, PG no longer varies across different scenarios, as all scenario-dependent variables become fixed due to the assumption of a constant target demand. Solving the revised objective function (4.2) provides the optimal build capacities of the power plants under deterministic

assumptions. These capacities are presented in the Table (4.1).

$$TC = \sum_{t,p} (PG(t,p) \cdot oc(p) + C_{\text{cost}}(p)) + BC(p) + \sum_t LS(t) \cdot voll \quad (4.2)$$

However, in practice, demand can fluctuate between multiple scenarios. The first-stage decisions based on deterministic assumptions may fail to meet demand in some high-demand periods, as they are based on average demand. When solving the model with fixed capacities from Table (4.1), the total cost is $Z_{DP} = 50.647$ billion Euros. This solution results in an unmet demand of 123,711.11 MWh, which is balanced through load shedding.

Technology	Build Capacities (MW)	% Share
solar	103,124	35.59%
windOn	101,812	35.14%
gas	53,494	18.46%
windOff	19,112	6.60%
battery	5,391	1.86%
biomass	3,677	1.27%
waste	2,424	0.84%
water	687	0.24%

Table 4.1: Build Capacities and Percentage Share of Different Technologies Considering Expected Value of Demand

4.1.2 Perfect Information Solution

In the perfect information scenario, where we have complete knowledge of future the demand pattern, the model is free to construct capacities that meet specific scenario dependent demand levels in the second stage. This results in lower overall costs. The objective function equation (3.1) is modified in to equation (4.3):

$$\min TC = \sum_{s,t,p} (w_s(s) \cdot PG(s,t,p) \cdot oc(p)) + \sum_{s,p} (w_s(s) \cdot ic(p) \cdot BC(s,p)) + \sum_{s,t} w_s(s) \cdot LS(s,t) \cdot voll \quad (4.3)$$

In this case, the build capacities are scenario-dependent, and the total cost is a weighted average across the three demand scenarios, including all cost components. The total cost for this perfect information case is $Z_{PI} = 49.853$ billion Euros.

4.1.3 Stochastic Solution

While the perfect information solution provides the lowest cost, it is unrealistic due to the inherent uncertainty in future demand. The stochastic model, discussed in Section 3, offers a more feasible approach by considering probabilistic outcomes of future events. The objective function in the stochastic model provides a solution with Z_{DP} and Z_{PI} as the upper and lower bounds, respectively. Figure (4.1) illustrates the comparison of costs between these three approaches, with the stochastic solution resulting in a total cost of $Z_{PI} = 49.984$ billion Euros.

4.2 Cost Component Analysis

The analysis of the cost components across the three solution methods—Deterministic, Stochastic, and Perfect Information—highlights several key findings (Figure 4.1) :

4.2.1 Investment Costs

The investment cost remains relatively consistent across scenarios and solution methods, with minor variations. This reflects the fact that the investment decisions are made in the first stage, before future uncertainties are realized. In the deterministic and stochastic cases, a single investment decision is made for all scenarios, whereas the perfect information model allows for scenario-specific investments. However, the differences remain small, suggesting the robustness of investment decisions regardless of demand uncertainty.

Figure 4.1: Break-up of the cost components under various assumptions of solution techniques

4.2.2 Generation Costs

Generation costs vary more significantly across scenarios, especially in Scenario 1, where deterministic and perfect information solutions exhibit higher costs. This indicates that both models struggle to accommodate Scenario 1's EV charging pattern (primarily at home), which creates higher demand at peak times. The stochastic solution, by spreading demand risk across scenarios, leads to a more balanced generation cost across all scenarios. Scenario 3, with smart charging optimization, consistently results in the lowest generation cost, as it better aligns with renewable energy availability.

4.2.3 Load Shedding Costs

The deterministic solution incurs notable load shedding costs in Scenario 1 (1.764 Billion) and Scenario 3 (0.091 Billion), which indicates that unserved demand is a significant issue in these cases. By contrast, the stochastic and perfect information models completely eliminate load shedding costs.

4.3 Model Parameters

4.3.1 Value of Stochastic Solution (VSS)

The value of the stochastic solution (VSS) measures the benefit of using a stochastic approach instead of the expected value solution. It can be calculated as the difference between the cost of the expected value solution and the stochastic solution.

$$VSS = Z_{DP} - Z_{SS}$$

The value of VSS which is equal to 663 Million Euros, quantifies the cost savings from accounting for uncertainty in the model.

4.3.2 Expected Value of Perfect Information (EVPI)

The Expected Value of Perfect Information (EVPI) represents the value of having perfect foresight about future demand. It is the difference between the cost of the stochastic solution and the perfect information solution, capturing the benefit of having complete knowledge of future scenarios. Value

of EVPI is 131 Million Euros based of the following calculation,

$$EVPI = Z_{SS} - Z_{PI}$$

Figure (4.2) depicts the values of VSS and EVPI and their relative comparison with the total cost obtained in the section 4.2.1, 4.2.2, and 4.2.3.

Figure 4.2: Total cost under various assumptions of solution techniques, values of VSS and EVPI

4.4 Comparing Build Capacities

The future build capacities illustrated in the Figure (4.3) are additional to the currently available capacities, and any capacity deemed sufficient or obsolete, such as nuclear, will not be expanded.

Figure 4.3: Comparison of build capacities between stochastic and deterministic solutions

The stochastic model generally proposes lower capacities for renewable technologies like solar and onshore wind compared to the deterministic model, reflecting a more nuanced approach to demand uncertainty. For solar power, the stochastic model suggests 102,491 MW (34.15% of total capacity), slightly less than the deterministic model's 103,124 MW (35.59%). Onshore wind capacities are similar, with the stochastic model forecasting 102,181 MW (68.20%) versus 101,812 MW (70.73%) for the deterministic model. These results show a consensus on the critical role of these technologies, though the stochastic model accounts for demand fluctuations more effectively.

In contrast, the stochastic model significantly increases the projected build capacity for gas-fired power plants to 64,518 MW, compared to the deterministic model's 53,494.1 MW, emphasising on the need for flexible, dispatchable sources to manage uncertainties in supply and demand. Despite this, both models show similar cumulative shares of gas, underscoring its importance for grid stability.

For technologies like offshore wind, biomass, waste, and water, the differences between the models are minimal, indicating that these technologies are less sensitive to demand uncertainty or have stable expansion potential. Battery storage also sees minimal variation, underscoring the growing importance of energy storage in dealing with the intermittency of renewable energy sources. The small difference between the two models shows that both recognize the need for storage but that the stochastic model provides a slightly higher capacity.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that some existing technologies, such as nuclear or hard coal, which currently provide significant capacity, are not expanded in either solution. This reflects the model's consideration of current capacity sufficiency, market trends, and policy constraints, particularly for technologies being phased out due to environmental or economic reasons.

4.5 Comparing Power Generation

When comparing the generated power, some conventional technologies are not newly constructed but leverage existing capacities to produce a small amount of power. The model utilizes these existing technologies to minimize investment costs and capitalize on their flexible generation patterns during peak hours in the deterministic scenario.

Referring to the Figure (4.4), the stochastic model prioritizes onshore wind, generating 670,185

Figure 4.4: Power generated by individual technologies: Comparison between stochastic and deterministic solutions

MWh (43.74%), compared to 618,453 MWh (40.34%) in the deterministic model. This reflects a more flexible approach to future demand variability. Solar power also benefits from this flexibility, with the stochastic model producing 256,962 MWh (16.77%) versus 233,600 MWh (15.24%) in the deterministic model. Both models show similar gas generation levels (stochastic: 344,090 MWh, 22.46%; deterministic: 340,464 MWh, 22.21%), emphasizing its role in balancing renewables.

Offshore wind generation diverges notably; the deterministic model produces 253,957 MWh (16.57%) compared to 179,384 MWh (11.71%) in the stochastic model. This indicates the deterministic model's overreliance on offshore wind, assuming stable demand. Biomass, waste, and water contribute minor differences between the models.

Interestingly, hard coal, which is phased out in the stochastic solution, contributes a small amount of generation in the deterministic case (2,417.62 MWh, or 0.1577%). This reflects the deterministic model's reliance on some legacy technologies to meet demand, even though they are not considered in the more flexible stochastic model. Reservoir storage and oil contribute negligible amounts of generation in both models, with almost no impact on the overall generation mix.

4.6 Build Capacities in Perfect Information Case

As depicted in the figure (4.5), these scenarios represent distinct assumptions about future energy demands, particularly in relation to electric vehicle (EV) charging patterns, which play a significant role in shaping the energy mix in the future.

Figure 4.5: Build Capacities under the Perfect Information Assumption

Scenario 1 represents the core assumption, where EVs are primarily charged at home. This scenario has the highest probability of 0.5, reflecting its centrality to the model. In Scenario 2, EVs are charged at both work and home, which slightly alters the demand patterns. This scenario has a probability of 0.3. The build capacities here shift somewhat, with solar capacity increasing to 110,874 MW, reflecting the higher daytime demand for charging at work. Onshore wind capacity decreases to 99,190.6 MW, while gas capacity also drops to 52,418.8 MW. The increased reliance on solar reflects the alignment of EV charging during daylight hours with solar power generation.

Scenario 3 assumes the implementation of smart charging for EVs, which optimizes charging times to better match renewable energy availability. This scenario, with a probability of 0.2, shows a further increase in solar capacity to 133,886 MW, the highest among the three scenarios, and a slightly lower onshore wind capacity of 95,806.8 MW. Gas capacity remains robust at 55,124.5 MW, while offshore wind sees a reduction to 17,592.1 MW. Battery capacity increases to 5,604.76 MW, reflecting the greater need for storage under smart charging schemes. The higher solar capacity in this scenario demonstrates the potential of smart charging to better integrate solar power into the grid by aligning EV charging with peak solar generation.

Overall, the build capacities across the three scenarios highlight the varying importance of renewable energy sources, particularly solar, in different EV charging patterns. Scenario 1, representing home charging, places more emphasis on onshore wind, while Scenario 2 shifts towards increased solar capacity to meet daytime charging demands. Scenario 3, with smart charging, optimizes for both solar and storage, showing the highest solar capacity but slightly reduced wind capacities.

5 Conclusion

The study project presents a stochastic power plant expansion model that incorporates uncertainty in future electricity demand, particularly focusing on the impact of different electric vehicle (EV) charging scenarios.

The comparison between the stochastic and deterministic solutions reveals minimal differences for most renewable technologies, with solar and onshore wind capacities aligning closely in both models. A more significant divergence occurs with gas-fired plants, where the stochastic model proposes 64,518 MW compared to the deterministic model's 53,494.1 MW. This reflects the stochastic model's recognition of gas as a key flexible technology to manage uncertainty in supply and demand. While offshore wind, battery storage, biomass, waste, and water show minimal variations, the differences in gas capacity highlight the stochastic model's ability to ensure grid stability under fluctuating demand.

These build capacities reflect the model's flexibility in adapting to different charging behaviors for EVs, demonstrating the importance of integrating renewable energy with smart grid technologies to manage future demand effectively.

The stochastic model provides a more balanced and resilient approach to power plant expansion, minimizing costs across uncertain demand scenarios. The perfect information model offers slight improvements but assumes foresight that may not be feasible in real-world applications. The deterministic solution, while simpler, struggles to manage demand variability, especially under the more challenging scenarios like Scenario 1. The correlation between EV charging patterns and generation costs indicates that strategies like smart charging (Scenario 3) can significantly reduce costs and improve grid efficiency.

While the model provides valuable insights, it is important to note several limitations. The primary uncertainty considered in the model is demand, whereas other factors such as fuel prices, carbon prices, and operating costs are treated as fixed. Furthermore, the model uses a discrete probability distribution, which may not capture the full complexity of potential future outcomes.

Despite these limitations, the learning outcomes from this study are significant. The stochastic programming approach highlights the importance of prioritizing stability and reliability in power system planning under uncertainty. This method offers a closer representation of real-world

conditions by accounting for variable demand scenarios. Additionally, the Expected Value of Perfect Information (EVPI) suggests opportunities for further research, particularly in exploring the benefits of more refined models that incorporate a wider range of uncertainties.

6 Appendix

Appendix A: Techno-Economical Data for Power Plants

Table A.1: Power Plant Investment Data

Technology	Annuity (€/year)	Lifetime (years)	Investment Cost (€/MW)
Solar	54,278.63	25	765,000
Wind (Onshore)	136,412.40	20	1,700,000
Wind (Offshore)	324,252.73	25	4,570,000
Biogas	243,942.88	30	3,750,000
Biomass	260,205.74	30	4,000,000
Lignite	110,728.51	40	1,900,000
Hard Coal	101,986.78	40	1,750,000
Gas (GuD)	61,798.86	30	950,000
Gas (Simple Cycle)	32,525.72	30	500,000
Battery	57,805.37	15	600,000
Nuclear	332,185.52	40	5,700,000
Waste	484,893.40	30	7,454,000
Geothermal	162,628.59	30	2,500,000
Water	109,553.47	50	2,000,000
Oil	130,102.87	30	2,000,000
Pumped Storage	235,539.96	50	4,300,000
Reservoir Storage	178,024.39	50	3,250,000

Table A.2: Power Plant Operational Costs and Emission Factors

Technology	Operational Cost (€/MWh)	Emission Factor (t/MWh)
Hard Coal	31.22	0.34
Gas	66.59	0.20
Biomass	27.46	0
Solar	0	0
Wind (Onshore)	0	0
Wind (Offshore)	0	0
Water	0	0
Nuclear	17.87	0
Waste	1	0
Geothermal	0	0
Lignite	9.86	0.40
Oil	94.80	0.28
Pumped Storage	0	0
Reservoir Storage	0	0
Battery	0	0

Appendix B: Digital Annex

The GAMS code, along with the complete set of input and output data, can be accessed from the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13761317>.

Appendix C - Data Sources

Data Source	Reference
Water capacity factor	Lehner, B., Czisch, G., Vassolo, S. (2001): Europe's Hydropower Potential Today and in the Future.
Investment costs power plant	Schneider, D. R., et al. (2010): Cost analysis of waste-to-energy plant.
Levelized cost of electricity	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems ISE (2024): Levelized Cost of Electricity.
Operation costs power plant	Energiewirtschaftliches Institut Universität Köln (2019): Merit Order Tool.
Efficiency power plant	Energiewirtschaftliches Institut Universität Köln (2019): Merit Order Tool.
Capacity factors renewables	ENTSO-E Transparency Platform (2024): Data derived from real power output of renewable plant types.
Power plant capacities	ENTSO-E Transparency Platform (2024).
Base power demand	ENTSO-E Transparency Platform (2024).
Scenarios	Boßmann, T. and Staffell, I. (2015): The shape of future electricity demand: Exploring load curves in 2050s Germany and Britain. In: <i>Energy</i> . 90, 1317–1333.
Storage capacities	ENTSO-E Transparency Platform (2024): Storage capacities data.

Table A.3: Data sources for the analysis

Bibliography

- Andersen, F. et al. (2013): Long-term forecasting of hourly electricity load: Identification of consumption profiles and segmentation of customers. In: *Energy Conversion and Management*. 68, 244–252.
- Boßmann, T. and Staffell, I. (2015): The shape of future electricity demand: Exploring load curves in 2050s Germany and Britain. In: *Energy*. 90, 1317–1333.
- Conejo, A. J., Carrion, M. and Morales, J. M. (2010): *Decision making under uncertainty in electricity markets*. Springer.
- Koreneff, G. et al. (2009): Impacts of electric vehicles on the electric power system in the Nordic countries. In:
- Möst, D. and Keles, D. (2010): A survey of stochastic modeling approaches for liberalized electricity markets. In: *European Journal of Operational Research*. 207 (3), 543–556.
- Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz (BMWK), B. für (2024): *Energiewende und Klimaschutz: Herausforderungen und Wege der Transformation*. BMWK Official Document, available online. Kabinettsbeschluss vom 20.03.2024.

Erklärung der Verfasser

Hiermit erkläre ich eidesstattlich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig und ohne Benutzung anderer als der angegebenen Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe sowie die aus fremden Quellen direkt oder indirekt übernommenen Gedanken als solche kenntlich gemacht habe.

Die Arbeit wurde bisher in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form keiner anderen Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegt und auch noch nicht veröffentlicht.

Dresden, 15.09.2024

Akshay Singh Yadav

Christian Tsenov

Rishabh Tiwari

Sebastian Trümper

Erklärung der Autorenschaft

Gemeinsame Autorenschaft

Hiermit erklären wir, dass am folgenden Beitrag

Optimizing Power Plant Expansion under Uncertainty: A Stochastic Programming Approach

alle Autoren gleichwertig beteiligt waren und daher keine differenzierte Erklärung der Autorenschaft notwendig ist.

Dresden, 15.09.2024

Akshay Singh Yadav

Christian Tsenov

Rishabh Tiwari

Sebastian Trümper